

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and Nonrelativistic Quantum Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 15, 2021

Although the idea of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ was known from the Stern Gerlach experiment, it had to be added to the Schrodinger equation by W. Pauli. It was not until P. Dirac linearized the relativistic Klein-Gordon equation that spin $\frac{1}{2}$ seemed to appear naturally in a theory.

In a previous note (1), we argued that not only does a photon solution (which emerges from the classical Maxwell electromagnetic equations with no charge sources and currents) have a wavelength and frequency $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ with $E=p$, but also an intrinsic physical sense of three space because E (the electric field), B (the magnetic field which is perpendicular to E) and p the momentum (which is perpendicular to E and B) form a basis for three-space. This is important because one may always choose the z direction along p (the momentum) so momentum alone does not intrinsically define three-space. De Broglie postulated that an electron has a wavelength like a photon. In (1) we suggested that perhaps the electron should also have an intrinsic physical sense of three-space. The Klein-Gordon equation, however, contains pp which is a scalar with the same value for a fixed value p pointing in any direction. As a result, three-space is not represented even if one has (p_x, p_y, p_z) . We noted in (1) that one may linearize the Klein-Gordon equation using a two vector if one considers p as p_z only. If one wishes to linearize with $p=(p_x, p_y, p_z)$ then one is forced to use four-vectors and $(s \cdot p)$ emerges in the equations where s is a 2×2 Pauli matrix such that $s \cdot p \ s \cdot p = pp$. Thus, linearizing the Klein-Gordon equation does not necessarily bring in spin. It is by insisting that p_x , p_y and p_z be present i.e. forcing an intrinsic sense of three-space that the s_i Pauli matrices appear. These are associated with spin, a kind of angular motion which creates a sense of three space within an electron.

In this note, we try to extend these ideas to the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation which is not linearized. We also point out that Eberlein in 1962 (2) already suggested spin is a “geometric property” of nonrelativistic Euclidean 3-space.

Photon and Sense of Three Space

Momentum is a vector which may always be taken to point in the z direction (by rotating the coordinate system). Thus the photon relationship $E=pc$ is a scalar equation which may be associated with one dimension. Maxwell, however, found that he could use his sourceless, currentless classical electromagnetic equations:

$$dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B \quad dB/dt = -\text{grad} \cdot E \quad \text{grad} \cdot E = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{grad} \cdot B = 0 \quad ((1))$$

to obtain a wave equation with the solution $E = E_0 \exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and $B = E_0 \exp(-iEt + ipx)$ with E and B being perpendicular to each other and to the direction of momentum. Thus, not only does one have a wavelength and frequency ($1/p$, $1/E$), but an intrinsic and physical sense of three-space given by E , B and p which form basis vectors for this space. “ p ” (momentum) by itself only defines one dimension.

It may also be noted that one may rewrite the electromagnetic equations for the photon in the form of a wave equation i.e.

$$d/dt (E + i B) \cdot k = -i \epsilon_{ijk} p_j (E + i B)_k \quad ((1b))$$

ϵ_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol from the cross product which becomes a spin matrix i.e. ϵ_{ijk} is the i th matrix with jk representing entries. ((1b)) shows that the form of spin is $(s \cdot p)$. This will be used later with the Klein-Gordon and Schrodinger equations for spin $1/2$ particles.

Momentum Energy Relationship

Einstein's energy-momentum equation is related to one dimension which lies along the direction of the momentum vector:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4 \quad ((2))$$

((2)) is transformed into the Klein-Gordon equation using $E \rightarrow i\hbar d/dt$ and $p \rightarrow -i\hbar d/dx$, but this equation also does not have an intrinsic sense of three-space. The Schrodinger equation may be obtained from ((2)) by using the nonrelativistic limit:

$$E = E_0 + m_0 c^2 \quad \text{where } E_0 \ll m_0 c^2 \quad \text{Then: } 2E_0 m_0 c^2 = p^2 \quad ((3))$$

As a result, the Schrodinger equation does not have an intrinsic physical sense of three-space either.

The Dirac Equation

The Dirac equation is obtained by forcing a linear form of the Klein-Gordon equation which is still consistent with that equation. In (1) we showed that if $p = p_z$ one may linearize the energy-momentum equation using a two vector i.e.

$$E - m = p \begin{Bmatrix} p/(E+m) \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{or} \quad (E - m) \begin{Bmatrix} |a\rangle \\ |b\rangle \end{Bmatrix} = p \begin{Bmatrix} |0\rangle & |1\rangle \\ |1\rangle & |0\rangle \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} |a\rangle \\ |b\rangle \end{Bmatrix} \quad ((4b))$$

where $b = ap/(E+m)$. ((4a)) does not have the form of a linear equation, but if one uses matrices as in ((4b)) one shifts the extra p and $(E+m)$ into a vector so there is an appearance of linearity. There is no spin in ((4a)) or ((4b)) and p lies only in the z direction.

A four vector and the Pauli matrices only appear if one forces p to have components in all three directions (p_x, p_y, p_z) . Then:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} |0\rangle & |1\rangle \\ |1\rangle & |0\rangle \end{Bmatrix} \text{ becomes } \begin{Bmatrix} |0\rangle & |s\rangle \\ |s\rangle & |0\rangle \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{where } s \text{ are the } 2 \times 2 \text{ Pauli matrices. } ((5))$$

In order for Dirac's equation to be consistent with the Klein-Gordon equation:

$$(\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{s})(\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{s}) = pp \quad ((6))$$

We argue that ((6)) demonstrates spin (related to \mathbf{s}) is linked to a built-in physical mechanism i.e. a kind of internal angular momentum which ensures three space is intrinsically sensed even if energy-momentum equations only contains pp . It may be noted that pp appears both in the Klein-Gordon and Schrodinger equations and so both should contain spin because both are linked to ((6)). In other words spin is not directly a result of linearization of a relativistic equation i.e. the Klein-Gordon equation because ((4a)) and ((4b)) show that such linearization with $p=pz$ yields a two vector with no spin. Spin seems to be linked to creating a physical sense of three-space within a particle such as an electron or nucleon. As a result, spin is not a relativistic property and could have been postulated directly from the Schrodinger equation without knowledge of the Stern Gerlach by only using the assumption that a particle must physically sense three-space.

One may see the effect of ((6)) in the Schrodinger equation by considering the arguments used in (3) to obtain the Schrodinger equation from the Dirac equation. Above in ((3)) we showed that it follows from a nonrelativistic limit of the Klein Gordon. In ((4b)) we argued that linearization of the Klein-Gordon equation really places an extra p and $(E+m)$ into a component of a vector so the Dirac approach “appears” to be linear while two factors of p are actually present if one combines the two equations which follow from the Dirac matrix equation. This is done in (3) namely the two Dirac equations are:

$$(E-V-m) a - (\mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{p}) b = 0 \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{and} \quad (E-V+m) b - (\mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{p}) a = 0 \quad ((7b))$$

where a and b are two-vectors. ((7a)) and ((7b)) may be combined to yield:

$$(E-v-m) a = (\mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{p}) [1/ (E-V+m)] (\mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{p}) a \quad ((8)) \quad \text{which is an equation quadratic in } p.$$

Using $E-V+m$ approx. equal $2m$ on has:

$$E a = [pp/2m + V] a \quad ((9)) \quad \text{because of } ((6)) \text{ i.e. } (\mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{p})(\mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{p}) = pp.$$

This shows, we argue, that ((9)) the Schrodinger equation (time-independent) contains spin i.e. $(\mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{p})(\mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{p}) = pp$ even though it is nonrelativistic. Thus spin does not seem to necessarily be linked to relativistic equations, rather it is linked to pp terms which cannot discern three-space.

Spin Projections

Given that spin is linked with the physical recognition of three-space and that any axis in this space has the same status as any other, one would expect spin projections about any axis to be the same. From a classical angular momentum point of view, this is unusual.

Eberlein 1962

In 1962 Eberlein (2)(4) noted that spin is a nonrelativistic feature linked to Euclidean 3 space. His two papers are largely mathematical. In (2), he quotes H. Weyl noting that spinors are deeply connected with Euclidean space.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue following (1) that a quantum particle like an electron or nucleon should have a physical sense of three space just like a photon which has the mutually perpendicular set of electric field, magnetic field and momentum forming a basis of three space. Momentum only represents one dimension because one may rotate coordinates so p lies along the z axis. Thus equations which only contain the magnitude of p such as the Klein-Gordon or Schrodinger equation do not exhibit an intrinsic physical sense of three space. This sense appears if one considers $(s \cdot p)(s \cdot p) = pp$ where s are the Pauli matrices. In other words one introduces an intrinsic angular momentum which senses all three directions of space. This result does not depend on linearizing a relativistic equation although $(s \cdot p)(s \cdot p)$ does emerge if one linearizes the Klein-Gordon equation by forcing p to have three components (p_x, p_y, p_z) . If one consider $p=p_z$ and linearizes, one obtains a two vector not a four vector solution with no spin. Thus spin is not necessarily associated with linearizing a relativistic equation - it is linked to forcing the term pp to sense three space. In other words spin $\frac{1}{2}$ may be obtained directly from the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation by forcing pp to sense three space i.e. to see that pp is really $(s \cdot p)(s \cdot p)$. The form $(s \cdot p)$ already appears in the photon equations obtained from Maxwell's classical electromagnetic equations without sources so it is not new. The photon, however, uses ϵ_{ijk} (the Levi Civita symbol of the cross product) as the spin matrix (i th spin matrix) and not the Pauli matrices.

We note that in 1962 Eberlein wrote two mathematical papers arguing that spin is a nonrelativistic geometric property of three space i.e. one does not need relativistic equations for spin to emerge.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Spin and Information (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. Eberlein, W. F. The spin model of Euclidean three space Amer. Math Monthly 69 (1962) 587-598 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2310821>
3. Shankar, R. Principles of Quantum Mechanics (Plenum, 1988)
4. Eberlein, W.F. Models of Spacetime (1965) <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Models-of-space-time-Eberlein/a36d610530190d8d0f98045d57dd2e659f1d7b5c>

